

CEPID Neuromat FAPESP

INVESALIUS NEURONAVIGATION SYSTEM

User Manual - Version 1.0

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Overview

The system integrates the [InVesalius Navigator](#) three-dimensional tracking capabilities and [robotic control](#). The control is achieved through parallel processing between the Invesalius Neuronavigator, a main message communication script, and a server for connection (WIFI or network cable) to the robot. These three components allow for co-registration of a 3D magnetic resonance image with the patient's actual head, navigation with the Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) coil to specific points on the head surface, and increased accuracy, stability, and repeatability of the procedure.

This document aims to integrate the initial knowledge for installing the software and hardware systems. The hardware includes the robot, the stimulator, the electromyography (EMG) system, the Polaris NDI for 3D tracking, models of the objects and the adapters for attaching the TMS coil to the robot's flange - the Tool Center Point (TCP) (see section J). The physical connection between them is carried out through an Ethernet router to create a local area network (LAN). The connection between the computer and the MagVenture stimulator is made via an RS-232 port. The system's operation is described in section M below. The diagram below shows the system's organization, with its components and the physical connections between them.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the physical components of the neuronavigated robotic system.

Software components

The flowchart below shows how the system components interact with each other. These components are configured by Python scripts that communicate with each other.

Figure 2. Closed-loop communication and control flow. A. Logic between the InVesalius Neuronavigator software and the robotic Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) system. B. Communication between system components, considering the threads of the graphics system and the messages sent to the robotic system. Modified from the available thesis [here](#).

The figure above shows the closed-loop communication and control flow between the InVesalius Neuronavigator software and the robotic Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) system. Initially, the user defines the location of the stimulation target in the InVesalius interface, and this coordinate is sent to the robot controller (via socket.io). The collaborative robotic arm (Cobot) positions itself on the defined target. The distinguishing feature of this system is its ability to handle "disturbances," specifically involuntary head movements during the procedure. Optical sensors ("trackers") continuously monitor the actual head position. If a movement is detected, the system instantly calculates the "compensation estimate", adjusting the robot position in real time to ensure that the stimulation coil remains on the correct brain target, despite the patient's movement. Finally, the corrected and updated position is sent back to the InVesalius interface for visualization.

Main components:

1. tms-robot-control
 - a. `relay_server.py`: The central server script responsible for exchanging messages between the components;
 - b. `main_loop.py`: A script that controls the robot.

2. `invesalius3`
 - a. `app.py`: Executes the Invesalius neuronavigation application, also providing the graphical interface for the user to execute commands for the robot. This application interacts with `main_loop.py` through the `relay_server.py` script.

Relationships and flow:

1. **`relay_server.py`** sends or receives data to/from each machine.
 2. **`main_loop.py`** runs continuously on each machine, communicates with `relay_server.py`, and passes messages to `app.py`.
 3. **`app.py`** sends messages, interacts with users, and performs interactive functions.
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Figure 3. Simplified textual representation of the interaction of the InVesalius Neuronavigator system.

A. Instructions for installing Invesalius (Windows)

1. Install GitHub Desktop from here [github](#) website
2. Consult the InVesalius readme to install the program ([official website](#))
 - a. For [Windows](#), install Chocolatey Visual Studio via the PowerShell command line.
 - b. Anaconda: Create and activate the virtual environment.
 - c. Download the precompiled version of Invesalius in `_cy.zip` format, version 3.11 for 64-bit systems.
 - d. Paste the extracted files into the `invesalius_cy` folder.
3. To install the robotic control programs, see item D below.
4. Run the batch program (`start-robot.bat`) to use the Invesalius 3 neuronavigation system. Further instructions on calling the InVesalius robotic control commands are presented below in section E.

B. Instructions for physical operation of the system.

This section will be organized as follows. First, instructions will be given for operating the NDI tracking cameras. Then, how to turn on and operate the Dobot CR-10 robot. Finally, instructions for the Invesalius neuronavigator.

NDI tracking system

5. Connect the NDI camera by plugging it directly into a wall outlet or by plugging it into a power strip (power strip).

Figure 4. Connecting the ruler to the NDI stereoscopic camera.

C. Instructions for setting or resetting NDI markers

Part One: General Instructions

6. Turn on the stereo camera, which must be connected to the computer via a network cable.
7. Open the software NDI Cygna.
8. In the File menu, select Connect To and find the camera to be used (P9-13719).

Figure 5. Menu for selecting the camera available in the Windows system.

9. To create a new marker, select the New button.

Figure 6. Select the button to create a new NDI stereoscopic system marker.

10. In the “New tool definition” window, select the “Blank passive wireless tool” option.

Figure 7. In the “New tool definition” window, select the “Blank passive wireless tool” option.

11. Click Scan and move the object to be registered in front of the cameras until you hear the beep indicating the end of the registration process.

Figure 8. Three-dimensional viewing window for registering the new marker. Move the marker in front of the camera until a beep sounds, indicating that the marker has been recognized.

12. Once the object has been scanned, its markers will appear green in the camera image. Click Save.

Figure 9. A green indicator shows that the new marker has been recognized.

13. Ignore the "Design rule check" warning by clicking Save again.

Figure 10. Confirmation dialog box to save the new bookmark.

14. Select the folder where you want to save the file and click Open.

Figure 11. Dialog box for selecting the folder where the bookmark files will be saved.

15. Name the file in a way that allows for easy interpretation, explicitly stating the object being recorded (which could be the reference glasses, the coil, or the probe) and the date the recording was made. Use the *.rom extension and click Save.

Figure 12. Dialog for writing .ROM files to NDI markers.

Observation: Each marker has an identifying label on the back. In our lab, the probe has the code 8700340, while the two crosses have the codes 8700449 and 8700339. The suggestion is to use these numbers to identify the ROM files and avoid generic names that depend on personal preference or external references that can be lost. See below the images of each tag currently used on each side of the head in the current setup.

Probe Vega (apontador principal)

Marcador bobina esquerda

Marcador bobina direita

Figure 13. Labels located behind the factory-installed NDI markers with the notation "unique model".

16. To make it easier to locate each component's file within Cygna itself, it's helpful to also change the name in the "Part Number" field by clicking on the automatically created name ("example_automatic_name" in the image below) and typing the desired name. To save this change, simply click the Save button (again ignoring the warning). It is

recommended to make this change as soon as the marker is registered to avoid future complications.

In the figure below, the file had the following initial name: name_automatic_exemple (for illustrative purposes only).

Figure 14. Dialog for identifying markers within the Cygna software.

In the image below, the file already displays the new name, which correctly identifies the component that was registered.

Figure 15. Definition of a unique name for the marker specified by the NDI factory.

Part Two:Coil Registration

17. Now, to register the coil, repeat steps 1 through 11. Then, click the Open button and open the probe file, which has already been properly registered.

Figure 16. Dialog for creating the 3D marker to be attached to the TMS coil.

In the figure below, you can see the two tabs of the two open files (coil: 8700449 and probe: 8700340):

Figure 17.Top of the marker settings window.

18. With both files open (coil and probe), click on the Registration menu, then on Select probe tool and select the probe file, as shown below.
-

Figure 18. In the Registration Menu, select the marker to be registered.

19. Click on the Probe button, which is only enabled after completing the previous step.

Figure 19. Button to register the marker.

20. In the Coordinate Registration window, enable the Enable Stability Trigger item, and then click Next.

Figure 20. Marker coordinate recording window.

21. When the message “Probe for a point...” appears, position the probe tip in the center of the coil and wait a few seconds. Then, click Next.

Figure 21. Marking the center point of the coil, to define the linear transformation between the marker and the effective center of stimulation.

Figure 22. With the probe and crosshair marker visible to the camera, click on Next.

22. Enable the Origin, Axis, and Plane items and click Next.

Figure 23. Window to enable types *Origin*, *Axis* and *Plane*. Enable it and click Next.

23. The message “Probe for a point...” should appear again. Keep the probe tip in the center of the coil and repeat the procedure at least two more times (wait a few seconds, click Next, select the Origin, Axis, and Plane items, click Next again).

24. Click the Finish button, which is only enabled after the process has been completed three times.

Figure 24. Window for repeating the procedure and recording between cross marker and probe.

25. On the Review registration screen, select Accept.

Figure 25. Confirmation window for triplicate registration

26. Disable the measurement volume display (blue button shown previously) and verify that the origin of the coordinate system, which was previously located on one of the cross markers, matches the position of the coil's center. If everything is correct, click Save again. This concludes the coil registration process.

In the figures below, the location of the origin of the coil's coordinate system can be observed before and after the displacement was defined, respectively.

Figure 26. As with the pivot procedure, the center of the coil will be represented in relation to the center of the cross marker. Situation before registration.

Figure 27. Situation after registration, with the marker's pivot in a cross shape off the original center. The *probe* can be used to confirm the correct location of the transformed center.

This is an important step, as the goal is to ensure that the **center of the coil** keeps localized on the defined target and contact with their head during TMS is maintained.

27. Completed! Use the resulting ROM files from this section to load the markers into the InVesalius Neuronavigator (section B, item 15).

-
28. Turn on the DOBOT robot using the button on the front panel of the robot's CPU. To use the Elfin robot (Han's Robot), see section M below.

D. Instructions for installing and using the robotic controller.

29. Clone the repository [biomag_robot](#) from GitHub
30. Before configuring, make a copy of the .env.example file and rename it simply .env.
31. Edit the .env file and define the robot type, the site (location where the system is installed) and other configuration parameters.
32. The first step is to run the relay_server.py script with an argument to set the server port:
`python relay_server.py 5000`
33. Next, run the main_loop.py script. Note: main_loop must be run using the Python console: `python main_loop.py`
34. After that, run the InVesalius app.py script with the --remote-host argument, specifying the same port as the relay server:
`python app.py --remote-host http://localhost:5000`
35. Note that each time InVesalius is started, the main_loop is automatically restarted.

Figure 28. Turning on the robot by pressing the button on the console attached to the base of the robotic arm.

Dobot CR-10 robotic system

36. Turn on the control computer.

Figure 29. Turning on the control computer.

37. To connect the robot via Wi-Fi, locate it among the available networks.

Figure 30. Confirming the presence of Dobot among the available networks for connection.

38. Connect to the robot via Wi-Fi.

Figure 31. Connecting the robot via Wi-Fi using the password.

39. Open Dobot Studio and click “Connect”. Then, access the settings and click “Remote Control”. In the “Current mode” field, select the option “TCP/IP Secondary development”, click “Apply”, and close the settings window.

Figure 32. Connecting the robot via Dobot Studio by clicking Connect (1), switching to TCP/IP (2), clicking Apply (3) and closing (4). At the end, the robot status should show as Connected (5).

40. If the connection is successfully established, the robot's status should be Connected, Safe-L5, TCP/IP, Running Log, as recorded below.

Figure 33. Robot's state after connection, already in TCP/IP mode.

Figure 34. In DobotStudio, clicking the Control button opens the window above, which displays the robot's coordinates.

E. Instructions for InVesalius Neuronavigator

41. The system requires the execution of three scripts: the relay server, the main loop (both found in the tms-robot-control project as relay_server.py and main_loop.py), and

Invesalius (app.py in the invesalius3 project). To facilitate its use, it is recommended to create a shortcut. To do so, create a .bat file based on the code below:

```
call C:\Users\[User]\Documents\environments\invesalius\Scripts\activate.bat more annoying
start "relay server" call python
C:\Users\[User]\Documents\GitHub\tms-robot-control\relay_server.py 1000
timeout /t 1 /nobreak
start "main loop" call python
C:\Users\[User]\Documents\GitHub\tms-robot-control\main_loop.py 1000
start "invesalius" call python C:\Users\[User]\Documents\GitHub\invesalius3\app.py
--remote-host http://localhost:1000
```

This file contains 5 lines of code:

- a. The first one activates the virtual environment called Invesalius.
- b. Then the server script is started on local port 1000.
- c. A one-second delay is activated.
- d. The main loop script, responsible for exchanging messages, is initiated.
- e. Finally, the Invesalius app is launched using the same port 1000.

Make sure to set the directories correctly according to the computer in use. Save the shortcut to the desktop for quicker startup. For example, the section of the file that appears as “C:\Users\biomag\Documents\environments\invesalius\Scripts” must be adapted to the file system settings of the computer where the system is being installed. To do this, replace the string [User] by the username in the computer being used.

42. In the example above, port 1000 is used. If a port is not defined, the program automatically runs on port 5000. Pay attention to the correct way to define the ports, which will be explained in more detail later in this document (in section G). To check the code, open PyCharm (or similar software like vscode) in the tms-robot-control project.
-

Figure 35. Open PyCharm or your preferred editor.

43. Check the `.env` file (the root of the `tms-robot-control` project) whenever necessary.
44. When accessing the code for the first time, it is necessary to define some important parameters that can be found in the `env.example` file. Make a copy of this file, define all the parameters, and save it with the `.env` extension. It is advisable to follow the suggestions contained in `env.example` itself. Below, you can see an example of the parameters used in our lab:

```
SITE= usp_coil
ROBOT= dobot
USE_FORCE_SENSOR= false
MOVEMENT_ALGORITHM= PID
DWELL_TIME=0.8
SAFE_HEIGHT=1000
DEFAULT_SPEED_RATIO=0.01
TUNING_SPEED_RATIO=0.03
STOP_ROBOT_IF_HEAD_NOT_VISIBLE=true
TUNING_INTERVAL=2
TRANSLATION_THRESHOLD=30
ROTATION_THRESHOLD=15
WAIT_FOR_KEYPRESS_BEFORE_MOVEMENT=false
VERBOSE=true
```


Figure 36. Locating the `.env` file that contains the robotic control initialization parameters.

45. It is recommended to use `MOVEMENT_ALGORITHM = PID` because the robot's movement relative to the patient is less abrupt.

Attention! The `SAFE_HEIGHT` parameter sets the position on the z-axis, in millimeters, to which the robot moves when the Invesalius emergency stop button (upward arrow button, labeled "Move robot away from head") is pressed. This is a crucial parameter for the safety of the procedure and depends on the experimental setup being used (height of the chair relative to the height of the robot base).

It is necessary to verify the safe height for the setup, considering the height of the chair and the average seated participant. The height is measured from the base of the robot to the height at which the coil can be lifted to a safe distance from the head. To determine a safe value for `SAFE_HEIGHT`, one can measure the height between the base of the robot and the head, then add the desired distance between the robot and the patient. For example: if the height (distance measured on the z-axis) between the base of the robot and the patient's head is 85 cm (850 mm) and the intention is to ensure a distance of 15 cm (150 mm) between the robot and the patient in case of emergency, a safe height of $850 \text{ mm} + 150 \text{ mm} = 1000 \text{ mm}$ (`SAFE_HEIGHT=1000`) should be defined. Another way to find a safe value is through the robot's own software, which shows the coordinates of the tip of the robotic arm. Simply move the robot to the desired position (at a safe distance from the patient) and check the Z-coordinate value, which is already displayed in mm.

46. Execute the shortcut created to run the initial scripts (`conda`, `main_loop`, `Invesalius`) and open Invesalius. In our case, the shortcut was saved as "Invesalius Robot" and its button was modified for better localization in the desktop.

Figure 37. Checking the shortcut that runs the scripts with the network pointers and connection to the robot.

47. If available, move the 3 command prompt windows to the second screen.

Figure 38. Viewing the output windows with the states of Invesalius, the robot, and the server.

48. When opening Invesalius for the first time, you should select the English language, as the Portuguese version still has some issues that need to be resolved.

Figure 39. Invesalius language selection window.

49. Upon first accessing Invesalius, you also need to go to Menu Mode, then Navigation Mode, and finally click on Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation. It's always a good idea to check this setting before using the system.

Figure 40. Selection of the Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation mode.

50. To connect the camera, go to Menu Options, Preferences, Tracker. In the “Choose the tracking device” field, select NDI Polaris.

Figure 41. Defining the tracker's name depends on the code found on the back of the camera used.

51. In the “Setting NDI Polaris Config” window, in the “Select the COM port or IP” field, choose the port corresponding to the camera to be used from the droplist (in this case, P9-13719.local). Then, add the file of the markers already registered in the corresponding fields:

- Archive of *probe* em “Set probe’s rom file”;
- Reference glasses file (associated with the patient's head) in “Set reference’s rom file”;
- Coil file in “Set object's rom file”.

The probe file is always the same. Pay attention to the head and coil marker files. To set new markers, see section C of this document (Instructions for setting or resetting NDI markers) or visit the link here [tutorial](#). After adding the files correctly, click OK.

Figure 42. Checking the dialog box for defining the markers to be used as probe (1), head (2) and coil (3).

52. If you haven't already set up any markers, open NDI Cygna and follow the instructions in section C of this document.

53. Still in the Tracker window, in the “Select IP for robot device” field, find the IP address of the robot that will be used (in this case, 192.168.1.6) and click “Connect”.

Figure 43. Checking the connection dialog with Dobot. Click Connect (1) to connect the robot.

54. If the connection is successful, the system displays the message “Robot is connected!”. Before proceeding with registering the robot, it is necessary to put it into free drive mode. To do this, press and hold the central round button on the robot itself for a few moments, until the lights, initially green, turn blue, indicating that the robot has entered free drive mode and can be moved manually. If this step is successful, proceed to item 56.

Figure 44. Robot lights: a) Before activating free drive mode (green) and b) In free drive mode (blue)

55. If the previous step doesn't work, you can also put the robot into free drive mode using the latest version of Invesalius. With the robot connected, click OK to close the Tracker window. Locate the Navigation Section tab. If your computer screen is small, you may need to close the Data tab by clicking the up arrow to view this section.

Figure 45. a) The Navigation Section is not visible because the computer screen is too small. b) The Navigation Section appears after closing the Data section (by clicking on the up arrow).

56. With the Navigation Section visible, click the down arrow. On the home screen of this section, two tabs appear: Coregister and Navigation. Click the up arrow in Navigation. Select the robot arm button with a padlock to enable free drive. In Invesalius, the button turns green, while the lights on the robot should turn blue to indicate free drive.

Figure 46. **A.** Navigation Section home screen, showing the Coregistration tab. **B.** Navigation tab opens after clicking the up arrow, with the “Free drive robot” button highlighted (blue). **C.** Free drive enabled (button turns green).

57. Return to the robot registration tab (Options - Preferences - Tracker) and click Register to register it for the first time. If the robot has already been registered, the Register button is replaced by “Register Again”, as shown in item (2) in Figure 20, which allows you to repeat the registration procedure if necessary.

Figure 47. Preferences window - Tracker with robot already connected (indicated by the message "Robot is connected!"), with registration button highlighted.

58. In the "Create a transformation matrix to robot" window, click "Continuous" and move the robot arm until the system registers approximately 500 poses. Click Apply, then Save. Save the file appropriately (easy-to-understand name and date) and finally click OK.

Figure 48. Screenshot of the robot's registration before the start of the process, indicating that no states were recorded (0 Poses recorded).

Figure 49. Example of a robot registration dialog after acquiring 668 positions (668 Poses recorded).

59. If you already have a saved robot registration file, after clicking Register, click Load, select the existing file, and click OK.
60. At the end of the registration process, you should see the message “Robot is fully set up!”. Click OK to finish configuring Tracker and close the Preferences window.

Figure 50. The Tracker window will appear with the camera already set up and the robot properly connected and registered, displaying the message "Robot is fully set up!". Click OK to apply the changes and close this window.

61. To familiarize yourself with the system, first open the image that comes with Invesalius by clicking on “1. Cranium.inv3” in the Imports Section, Load data.

Figure 51. A. Imports Section, where the Cranium.inv3 image is located. **B.** Head Tab of the Navigation Section to access the 3D mesh editing tools for navigation. See detailed instructions below.

62. If everything is properly connected and registered, at this stage, the head (reference glasses) and the coil should appear green in the image in the lower right part of the screen (if they are indeed in the area visible to the camera).

Figure 52. The head and coil icons appear green because they are visible to the camera.

63. In the Navigation Section, on the Coregistration tab, click Start Registration.

Figure 53. Invesalius tab for registering the image references.

64. In the image at the bottom right of the screen, titled “Volume”, ensure a clear view of the three points that should be recorded: Left ear, Right ear, and Nasion (the depression between the forehead and nose). To do this, move the image with your mouse, rotating and zooming it as needed.

65. Position your mouse cursor over the image, exactly at the point you want to capture, and right-click. A red dot should appear in the clicked area. After clicking on the ear (preferably on the *tragus*), for instance, check which side the red cross appears on in the other orthogonal images to ensure that the right and left ears are correctly registered. If the cross appears near the R (right), the point was marked on the right side (right ear). Then, click on the Right Ear button in the Coregistration - Image tab. The registered point icon will turn blue.

Figure 54. The image shows the right ear. In the lower right corner, you can see the red dot that appears after right-clicking. On the left side of the image, you can see the red cross closest to the R, which confirms that the marked point is on the right side (Right ear).

Figure 55. Select the Right Ear button after marking the point on the image to make your registration.

66. Repeat the process for the remaining points (first, right-click on the 3D image viewport, then click on the corresponding name button). When all three points are registered and the buttons are blue, click Next to proceed to the Patient tab.

Figure 56. All buttons appear in blue after the points are recorded.

67. Clique em Start Patient Registration.

Figure 57. Patient registration tab, with the "Start patient registration" option highlighted to begin the registration process.

68. Select the point you wish to record by clicking on its button, which should turn yellow.

Figure 58. Select the "Left Ear" button (in yellow) to register the left ear.

69. Position the tip of the probe on the patient skin, trying to get as close as possible to the points that were previously marked in the image. Make sure the probe is visible to the camera (its button should be green in the 3D viewport). With the probe At the desired point, click on Record Fiducial. Repeat for the three points required (*Right Ear, Left Ear,*

Nasion). The points already collected will have their button color changed to green. Then click Next.

Figure 59. The probe, head, and coil icons are green, indicating that they are visible to the camera. A green dot is visible on the nasion and a red dot on the ear, which were the points previously recorded.

Figure 60. After registration, the buttons for each point turn green.

70. In the Refine tab, check the error (in mm) associated with the fiducial registration in the FRE (Fiducial registration error) field. Ideally, the FRE should be less than 2 mm. If the error is high, you can try redoing the previous step. You can also refine the registration by clicking the Refine button. When the FRE is satisfactory, click Next to proceed to the Stylus tab.

Figure 61. The Refine tab shows a high FRE of 11.01 mm. In this case, it would be advisable to re-register the points on the patient (by clicking Back) or refine the registration (by clicking the Refine button, in blue in the image).

71. The process of refining the co-registration consists of collecting more points on the scalp, between 20 and 30 points, roughly following the point distribution in the 10-20 system. After clicking "Refine", the system displays a message to confirm that you want to improve the system's accuracy. Click "Yes". Then, with the probe positioned, click "Create point" to register the new point. When the number of registered points is greater than 20, click "Apply registration" and finally, "Done". **This step should be performed on a clean surface, free of internal obstacles around the head.** The system should display a message with the new accuracy values. Click OK to return to the Refine tab. Click Next.

Figure 62. Using the dialogue to refine the co-registration between the participant's head and the marker. **A.** Confirmation message to begin the refinement process. **B.** Spaced points along the scalp are touched with the probe. Click the “Create point” button. The co-registration will be refined by clicking the button *Apply registration*. Finish with the button *Done*. **C.** Message with the new system accuracy. Click OK to finish the Refining process.

72. (Optional) Position the probe as shown in the image: on the right side of the patient's head, with the metal tip pointing upwards, aligned with the head orientation. Make sure the probe is visible to the camera. Click Record. The head and probe, previously gray, should now appear green in the Stylus tab. Click Next. This procedure is optional.

Figure 63. A. Button *Record* highlighted (blue). B. Probe and head turn green after recording.

73. In the TMS Coil tab, click “Edit coil registration in Preferences”.

Figure 64. Tab TMS Coil.

74. In *TMS coil registration*, click on *New*.

Figure 65. In the Preferences menu, under the TMS Coil tab, you can register the coil (by clicking New) or load an existing registration file (by clicking Load).

75. Invesalius will display the message below. If the coil to be used has a figure-eight format (which is the case in our lab), click Yes to use the system's default object. If you are using another type of coil, click No and select the corresponding *.stl file.

Figure 66. Message displayed after clicking New.

76. In the Object Calibration window, click on the button of the coil point to be registered; it should turn yellow. Position the probe tip on the coil left border, trying to get as close as possible to the point indicated in the image. With the *probe* properly positioned, click again on the button of the point you wish to register. After this second click, the button

turns green, indicating that the point has been registered. This step must be done carefully to define the best plane in relation to the center of the coil.

Figure 67. A. The Left button turns yellow after the first click. **B.** The button turns green after the second click, because the Left point has already been registered. Automatically, the Right button turns yellow, indicating that this is the next point to be registered. However, it is possible to change the order in which the points are registered by clicking on the point you wish to register.

77. Select the next point and repeat the process until you have finished recording all three points (Left, Right, and Previous). Click Done.

Figure 68. All green buttons after registering the three points on the coil.

78. In Preferences - TMS coil tab, in the Settings section, set the values. *Angle Threshold and Distance Threshold*. When the coil is positioned manually, 3° is generally used for Angle Threshold and 3 mm for Distance Threshold. For a neuronavigated robotic system, positioning the coil with the robotic arm allows for better precision, so 1° and 1 mm can be defined. Click OK to close the Preferences menu.

Figure 69. Defining the Angle threshold and Distance threshold values.

79. Finally, click on “Proceed to navigation” in the Coregistration - TMS coil tab.

Figure 70. Click on “Proceed to Navigation” to start neuronavigation.

80. Typically, targets are determined by manually moving the coils. Click Start Navigation to begin navigation.

Figure 71. The highlighted “Start navigation” button (blue) changes its text to “Stop navigation” once navigation has begun.

81. With navigation enabled, move the coil and apply TMS pulses to the patient until you find a point that elicits the desired response. When this happens, hold the coil in position and click Create Marker.

Figure 72. The “Create marker” button is highlighted (in blue) in the Navigation tab.

82. Next, right-click on the newly created marker in the marker list and select the "Set as target" option to set it as the target. It is essential that the reference glasses and the coil are visible to the camera.

Figure 73. The newly created marker appears at the end of the marker list, right after the fiducial markers. When setting markers with navigation enabled, they are created in the "Coil target" category. Clicking "Set as target" defines the marker as the target. You can rename the marker by clicking the Change label.

83. With the target defined, stop navigation by clicking "Stop navigation". Attach the coil to the tip of the robot.
84. Click "Start navigation" again. Then, click the robotic arm button (without a padlock). Immediately after clicking, the button turns green and the robot begins to move.

Figure 74. The "Track target with robot" button is highlighted. With navigation enabled, clicking this button will cause the robot to move toward the target.

85. To create new markers, use the activated intersection crosshair and right-click on the surface, click "Create marker" (creates landmark), "Set coil target" (coil target that contains the coil orientation).
86. To change the orientation of the current target, exit navigation and use the Q, E keys (clockwise and counterclockwise respectively) to reorient, or move the height (use the + and - keys to zoom in or out respectively).
87. To rotate with larger steps, exit navigation and use Shift PgDown or PgUp (rotates 15 degrees at a time).
88. To move across the surface, with navigation paused, use the ADSW keys as movement directions.
89. In case of emergency, the robot's movement can be interrupted by clicking "Stop navigation". We can also use the up arrow button ("Move robot away from head"), which causes the robot to move upwards towards the safety height set in the file.env. Finally, the robot itself has a red button that the patient can press in case of emergency to stop its movement.

Figure 75. A. (1) Start/Stop navigation button. (2) Button that enables target visualization. (3) Enables coil visualization. (4) Marker that has been defined as the target, highlighted (red). (5) Button that starts and stops the robot's movement towards the established target. To the right of this, there is the "Move robot away from head" button (upward arrow button), which can be

activated in case of emergency. **B.** Current version of Invesalius, in which more buttons are observed in addition to those already indicated in A.

90. To use the system with a volunteer or patient, it is necessary to use a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) scan of the subject. Open the file in the Imports section, on the Load data tab, selecting the DICOM or NIFTI format, instead of using the Cranium.inv3 image already present in the Invesalius installation.

Figure 76. Example of loading a structural MRI of a specific patient, from the menu File > Import other files... > Nifti1 > file.nii > Open

91. Segment the patient's head image using the automatic segmentation tool for a magnetic resonance imaging volume by clicking on Brain Segmentation (MRI T1). Choose Pytorch and GPU, if available. The accuracy of the brain volume prediction can be set with the slider up to 100%. With the GPU, brain segmentation is performed in approximately 10 seconds.

Figure 77. Perform automatic brain segmentation using the segmentation plugin by clicking on Tools > Segmentation > Brain segmentation > Segment.

92. Create a new surface based on the mask generated in the previous step using the tool in the Configure 3D Surface tab. To do this, click the plus sign, select the newly created mask, and click OK. These steps can be studied in detail in the official manual of [Invesalius](#).

Figure 78. Creating the 3D surface from the segmented brain mask from the previous step.
(update)

93. To create the outer surface of the head, click the plus sign within the Select Region of Interest tab > Create new mask, change the threshold to mark the entire volume, with the least possible noise.

Figure 79. Creating the 3D surface of the head from a new mask with a threshold that encompasses all the brightness of the head (threshold 13-255) (update).

94. Next, repeat the procedure described from step 30. Define the fiducials on the reconstructed surface. Now, this is a real patient record. Be sure to follow the instructions in this document carefully to avoid problems during the TMS session.

Figure 80. Visualizing the fiducial points defined in the left external auditory meatus and in the seed in the magnetic resonance imaging of a volunteer.

95. Before closing Invesalius, click the floppy disk button to save the project. You can also save the bookmarks by clicking Save in the navigation section.

Figure 81. Click Save to save the project markers (fiducial and target markers).

96. As soon as you try to close the application, Invesalius displays a confirmation message. Click on the “Store session” option to save your changes.

Figure 82. It is always recommended to leave the “Store session” option enabled to ensure that the information has been saved.

97. In the next session, the saved project should appear above the Cranium.inv3 image, in the Load data tab. Simply click on it to proceed with the project.

Figure 83. Just above Cranium.inv3, you can see the previously saved project file (ProMED CT 0051.inv3).

98. When opening the navigation section of an existing project, it is not necessary to re-enter the image, patient, and coil records. Simply click Next at each step. However, if there are any changes to the experimental conditions, a new registration will be necessary. Simply repeat the steps described above.

Attention: Do not allow anything to come into contact with the robotic arm's structure.

99. Open the MRI image if it is not already open.

100. To begin navigation, click the “Start navigation” button, select the target from the list, enable the target button, enable coil visualization, and click the robot arm button.

Figure 84. Using the start/end tab of Neuronavigation (1), where you can enable the visualization of the target (2), the coil (3), define targets (4) and activate/deactivate neuronavigation (5)

101. Select the target from the list; if it has been created, it should be highlighted in red.

102. When exiting InVesalius (File menu > Quit or ctrl-Q), click on “Store session” to save the current state for the next session.

Figure 85. Using the InVesalius exit dialog, with the option to save the desktop state so that it can be loaded in the next session.

F. Instructions for installing and operating the pressure sensor

Part One: General Instructions

103. The [pressure sensor](#) must be integrated into the system with the aid of an Arduino device (or other microcontroller).

Figure 86. Sensor model used in the interactive pressure control system.

104. The sensor should be attached to the center of the coil using double-sided tape or another method of adhering.

Figure 87. Pressure sensor location in the center of the coil.

105. The .env file must be modified to enable it.sensorPressure is applied when Invesalius is run.

Part Two: Setting up the pressure sensor device

Figure 88. Circuit diagram for assembling and connecting the sensor to the Arduino.

Figure 89. Assembly and circuit for connecting the sensor to the Arduino.

Figure 90. Detail of the sensor connection to the Arduino.

Part Three: Software Definitions and Operation in Invesalius

```
.env
1 # Copy this file to '.env' and set the values.
2
3 # One of 'aalto', 'tubingen', 'usp_coil', 'usp_neurosoft', 'default'
4 SITE=usp_coil
5
6 # One of 'elfin', 'elfin_new_api', 'dobot', 'ur', 'test'
7 ROBOT=dobot
8
9 # Either 'true' or 'false'
10 USE_FORCE_SENSOR=false
11
12 # Either 'true' or 'false'
13 USE_PRESSURE_SENSOR=true
14
15 # Replace with your port (e.g., 'COM1' on Win, or '/dev/ttyUSB0' on Linux/Mac)
16 COM_PORT_PRESSURE_SENSOR= COM4
17
18 # Either 'radially_outward' or 'directly_upward' or 'directly_PID'. Recommended directly_PID.
19 MOVEMENT_ALGORITHM=directly_PID
20
21 # The duration in seconds to wait after the robot completes the movement, before the next movement starts.
22 #
23 # This is used so that the neuronavigation has enough time to send updated coordinates to the robot control software,
24 # and we want to base the next movement command on the up-to-date information.
25 #
26 # For instance, in Aalto, the time between consecutive coordinate updates from neuronavigation can be as much
27 # as 0.8 seconds. Hence, the recommended dwell time in Aalto is 0.8 seconds.
28 # The dwell time is ignored in directly_PID control; it can be set to 0.
29 DWELL_TIME=0
30
31 # The height in millimeters from the robot basis that is considered safe in that the robot can move to that height
32 # and perform rotations and movements in XY-plane without hitting the subject.
```

Figure 91. Enabling the pressure sensor feature in the Invesalius initialization file.

Figure 92. Enabling the pressure sensor feature in the Invesalius interface.

Figure 93. Navigation screen with the sensor showing the variation in pressure on the sensor at various levels, with the robotic control algorithm in operation (image modified to show the variation in values and colors of the display. The actual interface contains only one circular display).

G. Instructions for acquiring electrophysiological data

106. Execute PyCharm and NeuroMS.

Figure 94. Using the desktop icons, run both programs, PyCharm and Neuro-EMG.

107. Execute a script in PyCharm

Figure 95. Activation button for the Python script `control_TMS_magpro.py`.

108. After connecting to the robot's control server, prepare the system to receive the first code to begin signal acquisition by pressing the "s" key.
109. Start recording the EMG signal by clicking the "Start acquisition/stimulus" button.
-

Figure 99. EMG signal acquisition stop button.

112. Save the data in the Trace > Export > To EDF+ menu, assigning a numeric name depending on the target previously defined in InVesalius.

Figure 99. Export menu for data in EDF format.

113. Select the newly acquired strokes by clicking on their name + CTRL, delete the newly acquired strokes, and return to step 4 above.

Figure 100. Export menu for data in EDF format.

114. Accept the deletion of previously acquired traces.
115. To define the details of the acquisition channels, double-click the gray area that defines the setup.

Figure 101. Confirmation of the exclusion of the current traces.

Figure 102. Dialogue to define the details of the acquisition channels.

116. Click the Next button to proceed to body region definition and advanced details. Click OK at the end of the settings.
117. The amplifier parameters can be changed by double-clicking the gray area above the window (Device).

Figure 103. Dialogue to define the body region to be tested.

Figure 104. Dialogue to define the acquisition.

118. To adjust the impedance of the electrodes in contact with the skin, click the “Electrode Impedance Measurement” button or press Ctrl-Z.

Figure 105. Dialogue for verifying impedance at the electrodes.

119. During the acquisition process, monitor the creation of the EDF files to ensure that no data was lost or any acquisition run went missing.

H. Instructions for acquiring electrophysiological data with the Bittium NeurOne.

120. Run PyCharm and the Bittium NeurOne program.

Figure 106. Using the desktop icons, run both programs, PyCharm and Bittium NeuronOne.

121. Execute the stimulation control script.

Figure 107. Activation button for the Python script control_TMS_magpro.py.

122. After connecting to the robot's control server, prepare the system to receive the first code to begin signal acquisition by pressing the "s" key.
123. Start recording the EMG signal by clicking the "Start acquisition/stimulus" button.

Figure 108. Button to start the acquisition of the electrophysiological signal (Start button on the left highlighted in red) and button to start the electrode impedance display (on the right).

Figure 109. Control screen and impedance adjustment for each electrode installed on the EEG cap.

124. PyCharm/VS Code will issue 10 triggers to execute the two TMS pulses.

Figure 110. Bittium screen after firing and acquiring the 10-pulse TMS EMG.

125. After the pulses are complete, stop the acquisition by clicking the Stop button.

Figure 111. EMG signal acquisition stop button.

126. Save the data in the Trace > Export > To EDF+ menu, assigning a numeric name depending on the target previously defined in InVesalius.

Figure 112. Export menu for data in EDF format.

127. During the acquisition process, monitor the creation of the EDF files to ensure that no data is lost or any acquisition is missed.

I. Defining the IP addresses of the components

Since we are communicating with various components within the same system, we need to ensure that the transmission and reception of information is effective. Therefore, this section will explain how the components should be configured.

Static IP components: These are devices that do not have a changeable IP address. Therefore, to communicate with these devices, it is necessary to use an address that respects their IP range.

- Tracking cameras

In our lab, we use NDI Polaris VEGA cameras. These cameras can be controlled and configured using the NDI Cygna-6D Polaris Vega software. The camera is connected via a network cable to a computer with the software already installed. Once powered on and connected to the computer, the camera's IP address can be verified by hovering the mouse cursor over its name. **NOTE:** all cameras share the same IP subnet mask.

Figure 113. Defining the IP addresses of the NDI tracking camera.

- Bittium

Figure 114. Screenshot of the NeurOne Manager showing the address of the Bittium device to be discovered and connected to on the local network.

Dynamic IP components:

- Computers

To add new IP addresses to your computer, access the "View network settings" option in your computer's explorer. Identify the computer's network entry and go to properties. Look for the Internet Protocol Version 4 (IPv4) option.

Figure 115. A Windows dialog box that shows where to set the domain and IP address on the computer.

Go to properties, click on Advanced, and add two IP addresses, one with the camera's range and the other from Bittium (in the examples given, 169.254 and 192.168.200). NOTE: Do not use exactly the same numbers as the devices, only the same range. The last digits can be arbitrary.

Figure 116. Windows dialog box for defining the domain and IP address.

- Relay server

Figure 117. Menu for selecting the settings for calling the relay_server.py script.

Figure 118. Python script call parameters, including the local IP address and port.

- InVesalius

Figure 119. Menu for selecting the script call settings [app.py](#) (Invesalius Neuronavigator).

Figure 120. Python script call parameters, including the local IP address and port.

- Robot DOBOT CR-10

Figure 121. Dobot Studio's home screen. The gear button in the lower left corner brings up the settings dialog.

Figure 122. To open the dialog box that displays the IP address, click on the list on the left next to the name "Communication settings".

Figure 123. Dialog for defining the robot's IP address.

If you are using a wired network connection and the newly configured IP address does not appear, first confirm that the address accepts ping and that the response matches the screenshot below.

```

Windows PowerShell
Copyright (C) Microsoft Corporation. Todos os direitos reservados.

PS C:\Users\user> ping 169.254.111.190

Disparando 169.254.111.190 com 32 bytes de dados:
Resposta de 169.254.111.190: bytes=32 tempo<1ms TTL=64

Estatísticas do Ping para 169.254.111.190:
    Pacotes: Enviados = 4, Recebidos = 4, Perdidos = 0 (0% de
    perda),
    Aproximar um número redondo de vezes em milissegundos:
    Mínimo = 0ms, Máximo = 0ms, Média = 0ms
PS C:\Users\user>

```

Figure 124. Command window (cmd in Windows) for discovering and testing communication between IP addresses. Test being successfully performed with the computer in use and the device with address 169.254.111.190.

If the port is not correctly connected or configured, the error message will be similar to the image below.

```
PS C:\Users\user> ping 169.254.111.190

Disparando 169.254.111.190 com 32 bytes de dados:
Esgotado o tempo limite do pedido.
Resposta de 169.254.82.20: Host de destino inacessível.
Esgotado o tempo limite do pedido.
Esgotado o tempo limite do pedido.

Estatísticas do Ping para 169.254.111.190:
    Pacotes: Enviados = 4, Recebidos = 1, Perdidos = 3 (75% de perda)
```

Figure 125. Error message “Destination host unreachable” if communication fails.

Once you've ensured the address is correct, you can add the robot's address manually.

Figure 126. Dobot Studio login screen.

Figure 127. Defining a new IP address for the Dobot robot.

The address 169.254 should appear; simply click the connect option.

Figure 128. Click Connect to connect with the Dobot robot.

Figure 129. A message appears at the top of the screen in green indicating a successful connection.

If you are using two robots, it is recommended that you only use one wired. Therefore, the remaining alternatives are to use both via Wi-Fi (if using the same computer, you will need two Wi-Fi receivers) or one via network and the other via Wi-Fi.

J. Assembly of the adapter kit for TMS coils

Integrating the robot with the transcranial magnetic stimulation device requires the use of supports to keep the TMS coil fixed to the robot's effector tip. To achieve this, 3D printed components were designed.

The parts were designed and assembled to attach the C-B70 model coil to the tip of the Han's Robot Dobot CR-10 and Elfin robots.

The parts were modeled in a modular way so that they could be printed and assembled later using PVC pipe glue. This modeling method allows for stable 3D printing, reducing the complexity of each part. We thank laboratory technician Fernando Torrieri for creating the 3D objects and prototyping them.

The two parts screwed onto the robot flange differ depending on the robot's brand and model. The spacer and adapter have different distances and hole sizes for proper adjustment.

Components

The parts were designed to be assembled using the Han's Elfin Robot.¹Drum CR-10²or similar. All measurements must be confirmed before 3D printing, and test prints are suggested for adjustment. Use at the user's own risk. Always check specifications for screws and other products involved in assembly.

Component parts (files attached to this submission):

1. Spacer
2. Adapter (adapter&spacer_RoboElfin.stl or adapter&spacer_RoboDobot.stl)
3. Swallowtail (swallowtail.stl or swallowtailwithraft.stl)
4. Coil body (bodyAdaptador_BobinaMagVenture_C-B70.stl)
5. Adjusted rope (adjustedrope.stl)
6. NDI marker support (supportTMSLocalizer_sphere.stl)
7. Side support (optional) - (apoiolateralBobina.stl)

¹Page 17 of [Han's Elfin Robot Manual](#).

²Page 29 of [Manual do Dobot CR10 Series](#).

Figure 130. Assembly for the Dobot robot. Numbering according to the parts list above.

Figure 131. Assembly for the Elfin robot. Numbering according to the parts list above. The dovetail and the adapted cable are out of sight in the photo.

Figure 132. Dovetail position relative to the adapter body. Dobot support with coil on the patient's right side. Dovetail with the larger portion in front of the coil. Arrow pointing to the hole marking the center of the robot flange.

Figure 133. Orientation of the dovetail in relation to the adapter body. Support for Dobot with coil on the patient's right side. Dovetail rotated 45° counterclockwise in relation to the front of the coil. TMS marker support on the right side so that it is oriented towards the cameras when on the patient's right side.

Figure 134. Orientation of the dovetail in relation to the adapter body. Elfin support with coil on the patient's left side. Dovetail rotated 40 degrees counterclockwise in relation to the front of the coil. TMS marker support on the left side so that it is oriented towards the cameras when on the patient's left side.

Figure 135. Exploded view diagram of the 3D printed parts. Parts 1 and 2 are screwed together at the flange. Assembly 3-6 can be glued with PVC pipe glue. Pay attention to the orientation of part 3, which must have the larger space in relation to the hole facing the front of the coil, otherwise the assembly will be off-center in relation to the flange. Part 6 should be glued with the main orientation depending on which side of the printhead the coil will be used on.

L. Remote Control for MagVenture Stimulators

This section describes the procedures for using Python scripts to remotely control MagVenture stimulators. Always read the stimulator's instruction manual before executing any function from this Python package. **Since this is not an official package, its use is at the user's own risk. When working with this package, ensure that the TMS coil is not placed on any electronic device or in any location that could cause damage.**

Communication is done via a standard 9-pin RS-232 serial communication cable (see figure below). The female-to-female cable should be connected to the COM2 port on the rear panel of the equipment (A). If the control computer does not have an RS-232 output installed, it will be possible to check if there is a nine-pin output on the motherboard and install an adapter (B). Otherwise, a [PCI adapter card](#) can be installed (C).

Figure 136. A. View of the rear panel of the MagVenture stimulator, highlighting the RS-232 port (item 7 in red). B. Cable for direct connection to the motherboard (left) or C. PCI Express card to be installed on the motherboard.

After connecting the cable, the stimulator can be turned on. The interface language must be set to English for the MagicPy scripts to function correctly. To enable remote control, use the buttons below the screen to access the “Timing” page and set the Timing Control to “External Trig”.

The package can be installed by following the steps in the [online repository](#). This applies to both Linux and Windows environments. In the case of Windows, you will need to use Anaconda for package management and VSCode or PyCharm for editing and running the scripts. As a rule, Anaconda and the other programs should be run as system administrator to fully enable access to the serial communication port. An example of an Arduino script that emits TTL triggers can be found in the files attached to this submission.

Example of a Python script

Below are two examples of Python scripts that demonstrate basic command sequences for the remote control of the MagVenture stimulator. The available commands and their corresponding text outputs are listed below.

A.

```

1 import magicpy as mp # importa a biblioteca magicpy para termos acesso às funções do pacote
2
3 mp.list_serial_ports() # imprime uma lista de portas disponíveis
4
5 input("Portas listadas. Pressione Enter para continuar...") # Aguarda o usuário clicar Enter para continuar
6
7 stimulator = mp.MagVenture("COM1") # Inicializa um objeto que se relaciona ao estimulador
8 stimulator.connect() # Abre a conexão serial
9 resp = stimulator.arm(get_response=False) # Arma o estimulador para aplicar pulsos.
10 resp1 = stimulator.set_page('Train', get_response=True) # Muda de página nas configurações do equipamento
11 resp2 = stimulator.set_amplitude(15, b_amp=None, get_response=True) # Define a amplitude do pulso em porcentagem
12 resp3, error = stimulator.send_train(get_response=True) # Dispara um trem de pulsos
13 print(resp3) # Imprime a resposta com os parâmetros atuais
14

```

B.

```

1 import magicpy as mp # Importa a biblioteca magicpy para termos acesso às funções do pacote
2
3 mp.list_serial_ports() # imprime uma lista de portas disponíveis
4
5 input("Portas listadas. Pressione Enter para continuar...") # Aguarda o usuário clicar Enter para continuar
6
7 stimulator = mp.MagVenture("COM1") # Inicializa um objeto que se relaciona ao estimulador
8 stimulator.connect() # Abre a conexão serial
9
10 resp1 = stimulator.set_waveform('Biphasic', 'Normal', 3, 50, 1.2, False) # Define a forma da onda do pulso
11
12 resp = stimulator.arm(get_response=False) # Arma o estimulador para aplicar pulsos.
13 resp2 = stimulator.set_amplitude(50, b_amp=None, get_response=True) # Define a amplitude do pulso em porcentagem
14 resp1 = stimulator.fire(use_ttl=False, get_response=True)
15
16 print(resp1) # Imprime a resposta com os parâmetros atuais

```

Figure 137. A. Basic script for connecting, enabling the stimulator, and executing a pulse train. B. Script for connection, waveform definition, stimulator enabling, and single pulse execution.

Available functions

Connecting and disconnecting functions

connect(force=False)

Connect to the equipment via the RS-232 serial port. The parameter force = True disconnects and reconnects.

disconnect()

Disconnects from the equipment via the RS-232 serial port.

Functions for arming and disarming the stimulator

arm(get_response=True)

Enables the device to apply TMS pulses. `get_response=True` returns:

```
{'amplitudePercentage_A': 0, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, 0)
```

disarm(get_response=True)

Disables the device from applying TMS pulses. `get_response=True` returns:

```
{('amplitudePercentage_A': 0, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Disabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, {'Temperature': 24, 'coilTypeNo': 73, 'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Disabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}), 1)
```

Functions for obtaining information from the stimulator.

get_status()

Returns a standard dictionary with the equipment status in the format:

```
{'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option', 'SerialNo': 1425, 'Temperature': 24, 'coilTypeNo': 'C-B70', 'amplitudePercentage_A': 11, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0}, 0)
```

get_status2()

Returns a complete dictionary with the equipment status in the format:

```
{('amplitudePercentage_A': 11, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, {'Mode': 'Standard', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option', 'Temperature': 24, 'coilTypeNo': 'C-B70', 'amplitudePercentage_A': 11, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'originalAmplitudePercentage_A': 11, 'originalAmplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'factorAmplitudePercentage_A': 100, 'factorAmplitudePercentage_B': 100, 'Page': 'Train', 'trainOrprotocolStatus': 'Running'}), 1)
```

get_mode()

Returns the stimulation mode in the format: ('Standard', 0)

get_waveform()

Returns the waveform, in the format: ('Biphasic', 0)

get_current_dir()

Returns the direction of the current, in the format: ('Normal', 0)

get_ipi()

Returns the pulse interval defined in the equipment at that moment, in the format: (56, 0) (in this case, it was set to 56 ms)

get_baration()

Returns the ratio between the intensities of two pulses A and B, in the format: (2.25, 0). If the intensity is 8%, the first pulse will be 8 A/ μ sec and the second 24 A/ μ sec.

get_raw_info()

Returns all equipment information for command definition, in the format: ({'Model': '03', 'Mode': '02', 'CurrentDirection': '00', 'Waveform': '01', 'BurstPulsesIndex': '03', 'IPIValue_MSB': '02', 'IPIValue_LSB': '30', 'BARatio_MSB': '00', 'BARatio_LSB': 'e1'}, 0)

Functions for setting parameters in the stimulator.

set_amplitude(a_amp, b_amp=None, get_response=False)

Defines the amplitude in 'Standard' or 'Twin' mode. If only one amplitude (a_amp) is provided, 'Standard' mode will be selected. If both amplitudes (a_amp, b_amp) are provided, Dual/Twin mode will be selected. If get_response=True, returns a dict in the format:

({'amplitudePercentage_A': 30, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 68, 'Mode': 'Twin', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, 0)

set_train(reprate, n_pulses, n_trains, iti, get_response=False)

Define pulse train parameters. A train is a sequence of multiple pulses at a specific rate. Multiple trains (of the same type) can be sent successively. If get_response=True, return dict no format:

({'Page': 'Train', 'train_sequence_status': 'Stopped', 'Mode': 'Twin', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, 0)

set_page(page, get_response=False)

Changes page in the device console. The page parameter can take the following values: One of 'Main', 'Train', 'Trig', 'Config', 'Protocol'. If *get_response=True*, return dict no format:

```
{'Page': 'Main', 'train_sequence_status': 'Stopped', 'Mode': 'Twin', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Enabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, 0)
```

settrig_chargedelay(trig_in_delay, trig_out_delay, charge_delay, get_response=False)

Define the delay of trigger and recharging the capacitors, if *response=True*, return dict no format: ('Empty', 1). The connection to the device is made via this function. Disconnect before use.

set_mode(mode, current_dir, n_pulses_per_burst, ipi, baratio=1, get_response=False)

Defines the stimulation mode. This includes current directions, burst_pulses, and other parameters. Note that you can use burst_pulses to send multiple single pulses as a burst for each trigger-in. n_pulses_per_burst can only take the values: 2, 3, 4, or 5. Se *get_response=True*, return dict no format: ('Empty', 1) .

set_waveform(waveform, current_dir=None, n_pulses_per_burst=None, ipi=None, baratio=None, get_response=False)

Defines the waveform emitted by the stimulator. If current_dir, n_pulses_per_burst, ipi, and baratios are not defined, they will be read from the stimulator. This takes some time, so it's best to define all arguments. To use this function, the stimulator must be disarmed.

set_current_dir(current_dir, n_pulses_per_burst=None, ipi=None, baratio=None, get_response=False)

It defines the direction of the current. If *get_response=True*, provides the response: ('Empty', 1)

set_burst(n_pulses_per_burst, current_dir=None, ipi=None, baratio=None, get_response=False)

Defines the number of pulses per burst. If current_dir, ipi, or baratio are not defined, they will be read from the stimulator. This takes some time, so it's best to define the arguments. If *get_response=True*, return dict no format:

```
{'amplitudePercentage_A': 0, 'amplitudePercentage_B': 0, 'Mode': 'Twin', 'Waveform': 'Biphasic', 'Status': 'Disabled', 'Model': 'X100+Option'}, 0)
```

set_ipi(ipi, current_dir=None, n_pulses_per_burst=None, baratio=None, get_response=False)

Defines the interpulse interval. If current_dir, n_pulses_per_burst, or baratio are not defined, they will be read from the stimulator. This takes some time, so it's best to define the arguments. If *get_response=True*, provides the response:

('Empty', 1)

```
set_baratio(baratio, current_dir=None, n_pulses_per_burst=None, ipi=None,
get_response=False)
```

Define the B/A ratio. If `current_dir`, `n_pulses_per_burst`, or `ipi` are not defined, they will be read from the stimulator. This takes some time, so it's best to define the arguments.

With `get_response=True`, provides the response:

('Empty', 1)

M. Using the Elfin robot (Han's Robot)

Unlike the Dobot, the Elfin maintains an industrial style with a dedicated touchscreen module for controlling the equipment.

Figure 138. Turn on the robot by pressing the button on the robotic arm's console panel.

Figure 139. Activate the robot by pressing the touch screen on the robotic arm's console panel.

Figure 140. Check the initial positioning parameters of the robotic arm.

Figure 141. Define the robot's load capacity depends on the type and size of the coil and other components attached to the end of the robotic arm.

Figure 142. LED lights at the tip of the robot indicate free-drive mode, in which the robot becomes collaborative and can be moved manually.

Attachments

Main .env settings

1. The initial 3 items should not be changed.
2. Dwell time depends on the computer (0.8 is a reasonable value). Shorter dwell times can be used on faster computers.

3. A safe height is around 1000 (1 m). Use Dobot Studio to determine the most suitable height (measured 1 m from the base of the robot).
4. Default speed (long): 0.11 (percentage of maximum speed)
5. Tuning (near the head): 0.08
6. Stop if not visible sempre TRUE
7. tuning interval: 2s (To change the minimum distance, in InVesalius go to Preferences, Stimulator). Here, 2s means that every 2 seconds the robot will move to try to improve its positioning after it has already hit the target.
8. The translation threshold defines the distance from the target at which the robot enters the state of **tuning**: 30mm
9. rotation threshold: 15 degrees
10. wait for press in case of debug: FALSE
11. verbose = FALSE

Main constant settings (constants.py)

1. Public messages between system entities; do not modify other parameters.

Common problems and mistakes

1. If the connection to the NDI stereo camera fails, navigate to the users folder, users/[username]/.config/Invesalius, go to state.json (which reloads the session) and modify the NDI number (note the end of the *com_port* (from the available camera).


```

state - Bloco de Notas
Arquivo Editar Formatar Exibir Ajuda
"project_path": [
  "C:\\Users\\Documents\\MRI",
  "InVivo.inv3"
],
"tracker": {
  "configuration": {
    "com_port": "P9-13719.local",
    "obj_dir": "C:\\Users\\NDI_markers\\obj_dobot_neurosoft_130524.rom",
    "probe_dir": "C:\\Users\\Documents\\NDI_markers\\probe_vega.rom",
    "ref_dir": "C:\\Users\\Documents\\NDI_markers\\ref_googles_vega_new.rom"
  },
  "marker_tracker_fiducials_raw": [

```

Figure 143. Screenshot of the state.json file open in Notepad on Windows.

2. If you are having trouble starting Invesalius, such as a SplashScreen error, you can access the folder users/[username]/.config/Invesalius and delete the config.json and state.json files.

Related files (attached to this submission)

Python scripts for MagicPy (MagVenture stimulator remote control) - zip file 1

1. test_magicpy.py - script defining functions for remote communication

Scripts for triggers

-
1. TMS_paired_trigger.ino - script for paired pulses with two stimulators
 2. TMS_trigger - EMG_timeStamp.ino - triggers for TMS and EMG (time stamp)

Scripts for using the pressure sensor with Arduino and InVesalius (*.ino)

1. Arduino_PressureSensor.ino - directly reads the voltage values from the pressure sensor, for installation phase
2. fsr_invesalius_use.ino - publishes the converted force values via serial, for reading by InVesalius

STL template files for robot tip coil adapters - zip file 2

1. adapter&spacer_RoboDobot.stl
2. adapter&spacer_RoboElfin.stl
3. coil support.stl
4. adjustable end cape.stl
5. Coil c-b70 1.1b v3.stl
6. swallowtail (2).stl
7. swallowtail with flaps.stl
8. tms_marker_support.stl

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[https://www.brainstimjrnl.com/article/S1935-861X\(24\)00058-5/](https://www.brainstimjrnl.com/article/S1935-861X(24)00058-5/)
